

Deliverable: Description of data generated for Salmonella, Campylobacter, Shigatoxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC) and their AMR determinants

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: SVA

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Description of data generated for Salmonella, Campylobacter, Shigatoxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC) and their AMR determinants

This deliverable was compiled in December 2021, due to the pandemic and other delays the data catalogue is not complete as some isolates will be sequenced and delivered to the project in 2022.

Separate Excel file attachments specify the selected isolates (one file per category) including distribution between countries, years, and source categories.

The agreed upon inclusion criteria and priorities were as follows for each group:

Campylobacter

For *C. jejuni*:

- The years 2015-2020 have priority. When possible, the genomes should be equally divided over the years; randomly chosen among good-quality genomes.
- About 100 genomes from human infections per country, preferable known NOT to be travel-related.
- About 50 genomes per “group of sources” per country. Give priority to animal sources, but include genomes from food (meat) from the animals if not enough isolates from animals. Of course, this is just an indication and if a country does not have these numbers for all or some of the sources and cannot sequence more isolates in the coming months, then we will work with what is available.
- The selected sources are grouped as shown below

If a country has more genomes than indicated above, you are welcome to share all available genomes as these might be used in country/region-specific modelling.

For *C. coli*: gather all genomes available for the same sources as for *C. jejuni*, trying to have about 15-20 sequences per source and country (if/where possible of course), and to get all human cases available (which, according to the inventory, are <100 in total anyways, and are only available in a couple of countries). Portugal has more *C. coli* genomes and therefore a good data set of Portuguese *C. coli* genomes can be made.

Groups of sources (approx. 50 genomes per source per country):

Chicken
Cattle
Sheep & goats
Turkeys
Other farmed poultry (e.d. ducks, quails)
Pigs
Wild birds
Pets (dogs/cats)
Environment (surface water, shellfish and vegetables as proxy)

STEC/VTEC

All isolates from any sources. For human data we have decided to limit the analysis to the last 10 years, including 2020 (2010-2020), whereas isolates from non-human sources isolated earlier may also be included. The inventory is based on a general catalogue for all species deployed in Discover and then we've added specific columns for STEC. We have agreed that pets, wildlife and environmental samples should be prioritised for inclusion and for any sampling performed within the project since previous collections have prioritized human isolates and domestic ruminants.

Included sources:

Human
Livestock
Pets
Wild_animals
Zoo_animals
Other_animals
Environment
Fruit_vegetables
Drinking_water

Salmonella

Focus on six serovars: **Enteritidis, Typhimurium, monophasic Typhimurium, Infantis, Newport and Derby.**

Sequences of at least 25 isolates for each serovar in each non-human source and 50 sequences for each serovar in human source per partner (or all the available sequences if less). More sequences if available. Sequences from 2015-2019 should be prioritized (data from previous years can be included for those sources that cannot be fully covered otherwise). When possible, the genomes should be equally divided over the years; randomly chosen among good-quality genomes. For the human sequences, please provide only those from non-travel and non-outbreak related cases, if known. For the non-human sequences, if possible, please prioritize those from the animals themselves instead of the foods thereof.

Included sources:

Human
Pigs
Cattle
Sheep/goats
Chicken (broilers)
Layers
Turkeys
Ducks/goose
Pets (dogs/cats)
Pets (reptiles)
Wild animals
Horses
Shellfish
Environment

Sequences from the environment, pets and wildlife of high priority.

AMR

All *E. coli* ESBL strains recovered from livestock, pet, wildlife, zoo animal, human, food or environmental samples collected by partner institutions during the period 2013-20 and identified using antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) and/or detection of ESBL genes. Only AST results and ESBL-gene detection results were collected (no WGS data collected).